

AEROTHERMAL CHARACTERIZATION OF A COMPACT HEAT EXCHANGER ELEMENT BY ADDITIVE MANUFACTURING

F. Ascione⁽¹⁾, A. Conrozier⁽²⁾, A. Sakly⁽³⁾, P. Planquart⁽¹⁾, J.M. Hugo⁽²⁾, D. Laboureur^(1*)

⁽¹⁾ von Karman Institute, Waterloostraat 62 – Sint-Genesius-Rhode (Belgium)

⁽²⁾ Temisth, Technoparc des Florides, 13700 Marignane (France)

⁽³⁾ AddUp, 5 Rue Bleue, 63118 Cébazat (France)

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ABSTRACT:

This paper presents the results of the aerothermal characterization of two additive manufactured off-set strip fins Compact Heat Exchanger (CHX) modules, in the framework of the European project NATHENA (New Additive Manufactured Heat Exchangers for Aeronautics). The two samples, with the same dimensions and internal fins geometry, differ for the material: one is Aluminium and the other is Inconel. Both samples were manufactured by AddUp. The experimental campaign was performed by the von Kármán Institute for fluid-dynamics (VKI) to analyze the influence of the material on heat transfer coefficient and total pressure drop along the channel. The results were compared with the outcomes of the CFD simulations performed by TEMISTh. Local fluid temperature and velocity as well as a non-dimensional study, in terms of Colburn factor j and Fanning Factor f are also examined.

1. INTRODUCTION

Compact Heat Exchangers (CHX) are a new generation of heat exchangers developed thanks to the rising of the Additive Manufacturing (AM), which ensures high design flexibility in terms of complex internal fins shape and new channels arrangements. In the last years, the aerospace industry is involving several resources in the research of more efficient technologies for the reduction of noise and pollution. Modern passengers' aircrafts fly at higher altitudes, where the air density is lower. Consequently, the installed air conditioning system needs larger airflow rates for a fixed amount of exchangeable heat power. In the framework of the heat transfer, CHXs represent a new frontier as they embody a perfect compromise of compactness and thermal efficiency. Compactness, expressed in terms of surface area density $\eta=A/V$, is the main feature. Extended

internal surfaces are used to enlarge the surface area-to-volume ratio with different configurations, such as: plate-fin or tube-fin CHXs. The design of internal complex fins shape and arrangement is translated in terms of global minimization of the device volume, better temperature control and lower weight. Plate and fins CHXs are widely used for gas to gas applications. The purpose is to induce several sudden changes of the flow direction, generating an increase of the heat transfer coefficient but consequently, also of the pressure drop. Hence, it is necessary to study both the effects and perform a design which guarantees a compromise between them. The current study is an investigation on off-set strip fins geometry CHX modules where the aerothermal properties are strictly related to the flow field, hence on geometrical parameters of the fins, such as: spacing (s), height (h), length (l) and thickness (t) (Fig. 1). These dependencies are studied non-dimensionally in terms of Colburn factor j and Fanning factor f , as function of dimensionless geometrical groups used to identify the accounted geometry: $\alpha=s/h$, $\beta=t/l$, $\delta=t/s$, $\gamma=d/l$, where d is the flow length. The aspect ratio α is inversely proportional to both f and j , independently from the flow regimes [2]. In literature, several experimental and numerical studies are illustrated and empirical correlations developed to model the dependence of the aerothermal physic on the geometrical characteristics. The most important experimental data-set was provided by Kay and London [2].

Figure 1 Geometrical configuration of an off-set strip fins CHX module

Manson did the first trial to develop predictive equations from experimental data-set on different geometries. Wieting [6] established correlations on 22 different geometries, but he neglected the analysis of the transition region. This flow regime was taken into account by Joshi [1], including the

* Delphine.laboureur@vki.ac.be

effects of the burred fin end and the roughness of the walls of the off-set strip fins channel. Mochizuki [7] modified Wieting correlation to fit his experimental data. Manglik and Bergles [8] worked on the data by Kay and London to develop predictive equations in all the flow regimes. Dong et al. [9] considered also the fin length influence, included in the γ parameter, related to the entry flow effect of the short fins arrangement.

The development of the AM has modified the properties of the prototypes; hence, new investigations are necessary to characterize the thermal hydraulic performances of the 3D printed samples.

Simplified geometries of straight [13] and wavy micro channels [14] manufactured by direct laser metal sintering were investigated experimentally. The fanning factor for straight channels showed an evolution similar to what can be found in channel flows with an important roughness [12], and showed that the equivalent sand grain size needed to reproduce the experimental results in turbulent regime using the Colebrook correlation was approximately an order of magnitude larger than the relative arithmetic mean roughness [13]. The wavy channels showed enhanced heat transfer compared to the straight channels, for a similar friction factor augmentation, opening the door to optimization of the heat transfer to friction ratio by using more sophisticated channel configurations.

As part of the European program CLEAN SKY 2, the project NATHENA (New Additive Manufacturing Heat Exchanger for Aeronautic) concerns the design and testing of a high thermal efficiency CHX for aircraft air conditioning system, exploiting the advantages of the AM. The present work discusses the aerothermal performances of off-set strip fins single channels for a plate and fins CHX. The experimental campaign was performed by the von Kármán Institute for fluid-dynamics (VKI) and the results compared with the outcomes of the CFD simulations by TEMISTh. Global pressure drop and heat transfer coefficient of the channel were analysed as function of different flow rates. Samples in aluminium and nickel alloys (Fig. 2) were tested to evaluate the effect of the material in terms of thermal conductivity and surface roughness. In addition, dimensionless correlations were used to compare with both the experimental and numerical results with databases available in literature.

Figure 2 Aluminium 3D printed off-set strip fins CHX module

2. EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP

The testing facility has been designed and developed at the VKI laboratories. The most challenging aspect of the experimental investigation was performing flow aeraulic and thermal measurements inside an off-set strip fins and plate single CHX module, due to the reduced sample dimensions.

2.1. Apparatus

Figure 3 Schematic of the facility

Fig. 3 shows a schematic of the main components of the set-up. Compressed air, from the 7 bar line, supplies the facility through a flexible pipe. The mass flow is regulated with three rotameters in a range up to 20 g/s. A divergent is used as a connection to a rectangular cross section metallic pipe, which is directly linked to the test section. Downstream of the divergent, a bronze porous plate is installed to guarantee a uniform flow in the test section. The length of the connecting metallic pipe has been settled, in the design phase, to ensure a fully developed velocity profile at the inlet of the CHX module.

2.2. Test section

The test section consists of the CHX module instrumented with the probes needed for its thermal and aeraulic characterization. The 3D printed samples tested during the experimental campaign have the same internal geometry, but one is in aluminium alloy and the other is in nickel alloy to investigate on the influence of the material on the thermal performances. Briefly, the main properties of these two materials are described as follows:

- AS7G06: aerospace aluminium alloy with low weight, high resistance to corrosion and excellent heat and electricity conduction.
- Inconel 718 (IN718): aerospace nickel-based super-alloy with good resistance to oxidation, corrosion and high strength in temperature ranges from cryogenic up to ≈ 1000 K.

Internally, the CHX module is composed of 15 rows each one of 20 fins in an off-set strip configuration. Its dimensions are 52 mm \times 18 mm \times 120 mm and the fins occupy an effective length equal to 100 mm. The top wall thickness is 1 mm whereas the bottom wall thickness is 2 mm. The fins are spaced of 2 mm with a height equal to 15 mm and a thickness of 0.5 mm.

A Laser Powder-Bed Fusion (LPBF) machine AddUp FormUp™ 350 was used to print the samples. The build volume of the printer is 350 mm x 350 mm x 350 mm equipped by a roller layering system. Fine powders with grain size in the range of 5 – 25 μ m were selected for the AS7G06 and IN718 materials. A specific set of process-parameters was developed in order to print a very fine walls (0.6 mm) and improve the surface roughness. Before printing parts, numerical thermomechanical simulations using Netfabb software were performed. The simulations results (materials deformation, residual stress and thermal distribution) have helped to define the printing orientation and the support design. The parts were used net-shape, without surface finishing.

2.3 Instrumentation

The pressure drop along the sample is monitored using a row of five pressure taps with a 0.4 mm diameter located on one side of the channel. The pressure difference between each pressure tap is measured using a pressure transducer, whose membranes have a maximum pressure sensitivity equal to 2700 Pa. Fig. 4 shows a schematic of the instrumented test section used for the measurements.

Figure 4 Schematic of the test section

The inlet air temperature is measured using a rake of four type-K thermocouples, located one on each side of the inlet rectangular cross section. The outlet

temperature is monitored using nine thermocouples type K, positioned on a cross shaped rake. A row of five thermocouples type K is located along the CHX module, on the opposite side of the pressure taps, to detect the temperature of the flow blown inside the channel during the test. A heating plate in Copper, of 0.2 mm thickness, is glued on the top side of the CHX sample. Supplied by a DC generator, it provides heat, through Joule effect, to the air flowing inside the sample. Its dimensions are 15 mm \times 100 mm to cover all the length occupied by the fins in the sample. The plate is fixed on the module using a very high conductivity paste OMEGA™ 201, to reduce a possible effect of the contact resistance. The temperature of the wall in contact with the heating plate is measured using a row of five type-K thermocouples glued on the top wall of the sample. Insulation has been adopted to cover the CHX element on the sides and the top wall to make negligible any effect of heat dispersion by both radiation and natural convection with the ambient. The IR camera is used as a non-intrusive measurement technique to study the temperature distribution over the bottom surface of the sample. Velocity profile measurements at the inlet and outlet sections of the CHX module have been performed using a constant temperature hot wire probe with a Tungsten wire. The probe was placed in the middle of the cross-section of the channel and moved vertically by a transverse system.

2.3. Testing conditions

The experimental campaign has been led in the same working conditions for both the two samples. The operating mass flow range is up to 20 g/s. For the thermal analysis, the heating plate supplied a constant Joule power equal to 130 W. The pressure was measured at ambient temperature to neglect the influence of the temperature in the air density. The data analyses the heat transfer coefficient as function of the mass flow rate for the different materials, and the total pressure drop as dependent on the surface roughness of each sample.

3. CFD analysis

CFD codes are more frequently used to predict and analyze the performance of heat transfer and fluids mechanical problems. They offer significant advantage such as reduction of time and cost of studies, and easily access to all physical results at any point of configuration (temperature, velocities, pressure ...). A numerical model using Starccm+ is used in this paper in order to compare the experimental results with the numerical performances. A similar geometry and operating conditions (Figure 5) to the experiments test are carrying out using a three-dimensional model, incompressible, steady flow with *k-epsilon* approach as turbulent model. A half channel is studied with symmetric conditions on solid and air side. A constant heat flux is fixed on the top of channel

equal to 65 W and variable temperatures depending on the flow and material conditions at other side of channel. The inlet flow temperature is uniform and with a value similar to the ones obtained experimentally. The inlet velocity profile is based on the measured experimental profiles, only imposing the vertical profile for the velocity, uniform along the channel width. Concerning the number of cells, a mesh study is accomplished to reduce the number of cells and by the following the operating time while conserving a Y^+ between 5 and 30, the total number of cells is between 7 and 8 million cells. Simulations are considered convergent when the residuals characterized the continuity and momentum equations became lower than 10^{-4} and lower than 10^{-6} for the energy equation and the difference between heat duty (air and wall side) was less than 0,3 %.

Figure 5 Simulated geometry and boundary conditions

Roughness effects were not included in the numerical simulation. The interest in this first computational study was to better understand the major flow features, as well as how much the flow and heat transfer is influenced by the roughness imposed by the manufacturing process.

4. AERAUIC ANALYSIS

The aeraulic analysis includes pressure drop and velocity profile. These measurements were performed without heating to provide measurements without heat transfer. However, in this range of flow rate and heat power, the pressure drop measurements were showed to be independent of the heating.

4.1. Velocity profile measurements

The velocity profile has been characterized using the hot wire anemometry. The probe used for the measurements is a hot-wire with a Tungsten single wire. The measurements have been executed placing the probe in the middle of the rectangular cross-section of the duct at a distance of 4 mm on a transverse system moving the hot-wire vertically, through an electric motor commanded by a LabVIEW code. The acquisition was set at each vertical step of the probe equal to 2 mm, at a frequency of 25 kHz. The experimental matrix consists of measurements of the velocity profiles at the inlet section of the CHX module for four different mass flow rates, respectively equal to 5 g/s, 10 g/s,

15 g/s, and 20 g/s. The same conditions were used for the characterization of the outlet section velocity profiles for both the Aluminium and the Inconel CHX samples. In the following sections, the results are examined in terms of velocity and turbulence intensity to analyse the effect of the presence of the fins in the sample only for one reference case corresponding to $\dot{m} = 10$ g/s (Fig. 6, 7).

Figure 6 . Inlet and outlet velocity profiles for $m = 10$ g/s

Figure 7 Inlet and outlet turbulence intensity profiles for $m = 10$ g/s

The velocity profiles assume the typical shape of a fully developed pipe flow. The curves are symmetric: the velocity reaches a maximum value in correspondence of the channel axis, then it decreases in proximity of the upper and lower walls of the channel, because of the friction effect generated by the lateral sides. The turbulence intensity (TI) has been evaluated as the ratio between the standard deviation of the velocity fluctuation and the maximum velocity of the inlet velocity profile. The trends appear symmetric with respect to the channel central axis for all the cases. All the plots have the same behaviour: there is an increase of the TI in the near wall region, followed by a rapid, almost logarithmic decay and a change of slope until the axis of the channel. This shape is

typical of confined internal pipe flow. In particular, the rising of the TI in the logarithmic region is the evidence that the turbulent actions are confined in the region adjacent to the walls: here, the low momentum fluid interacts with the regions at higher velocity, generating a momentum exchange of the fluid particles which initiate turbulence in the form of longitudinal velocity fluctuations [10].

The measured inlet velocity profile was used as boundary condition for the inlet velocity in the CFD simulation, with the difference that only the vertical evolution is imposed. The analysis considers a comparison between the inlet and the outlet velocity profiles of both the materials. The velocity profiles appear flatter in the middle of the channel in both the cases. Regarding the TI, in both the cases, the same trend is obtained (Fig.7). It is possible to analyse the effect of the presence of the CHX on the TI levels: due to the tiny dimensions of the fins and their distance, the result of the presence of the CHX module can be treated as the one of a porous plate [11]. It straightens the flow, decreasing the outlet TI levels so that the flow is more uniform and this influence is more significant as the mass flow rate increases.

Figure 8 CFD velocity magnitude contour at centerline for Inconel, 10 g/s

The roughness of the external walls is visible on the experimental profiles. As in the CFD, smooth walls are considered, the presence of the CHX module also acts as a porous plate, straightening the flow and decreasing the outlet TI, but also disturbing the initial velocity profile, already after the first layer of fins, as observed in Fig. 8. This explains why the thickness of the boundary layer at the exit of the CHX module is so thin in the CFD (where roughness effects are not modelled).

4.2. Pressure drop

For both the Aluminium and the Inconel 718 samples, the flow static pressure has been measured using the five pressure taps mounted along the sample. Due to the difference of the material, hence the surface roughness, the total pressure drop is expected to be different for the two CHX channels. The profile surface roughness (Ra) is the most common parameter used to characterize the surface refinement of a material. The results show higher values of the roughness for the sample in Aluminium ($Ra=27 \mu\text{m}$) than for the Inconel ($Ra=13 \mu\text{m}$). The local pressure drop between each pressure tap has been measured using a pressure

transducer. The total pressure drop is obtained as the difference between the outlet atmospheric pressure and the static pressure determined in correspondence of the first pressure tap, closest to the inlet section. The results of the measurements show a similar behaviour for both the cases: the total pressure drop increases with the air mass flow rate, and is always higher for Aluminium with respect to the Inconel (Fig. 9). The main reason of this results is the surface roughness, which represents the only substantial difference between the two samples, as they have the same internal geometry of the fins. Comparing the evolution of the pressure inside the CHX module with the CFD results, it can be observed that a good agreement is found with the Inconel at 10g/s, whereas for Aluminium, as well as for both materials at 20 g/s, the CFD under predicts the experimental evolution even though the linear evolution of the pressure over the channel length is simulated (Fig. 9). The discrepancies between CFD and experiments is increasing with the flow rate as the effect of the wall roughness on friction becomes more and more important as the Reynolds increases and the flow reaches a fully turbulent state.

Figure 9 Comparison of pressure evolution in the Aluminium and Inconel CHX modules for 2 flow rates: 10 and 20 g/s

To compare the results with existing correlations and better understand the difference in flow regimes, the pressure drop is examined in terms of Fanning factor f as function of the Reynolds number. The Fanning factor is defined as the ratio between the wall shear stress and the flow kinetic energy per unit of volume:

$$f = \frac{\Delta p D_h}{2 \rho u^2 L} \quad (1)$$

where L is the longitudinal length of the sample. The hydraulic diameter was computed according to Manglik and Berges, as well as the velocity:

$$D_h = \frac{4shl}{2(sl+hl+th)+ts} \quad (2)$$

$$u = \frac{\dot{m}}{\rho sh N_{fin}} \quad (3)$$

Correlations are used to analyse the dependence of the CHX performances on the fins geometry. Manglik and Berges [8] correlated the results of their experiments on 18 different geometries in aluminium, with an accuracy of $\pm 20\%$ through the following equations, valid for all the flow regimes from laminar to turbulent:

$$f = 9.6243 Re^{-0.7422} \alpha^{-0.1856} \beta^{0.3053} \delta^{-0.2659} \times [1 + 7.669 \cdot 10^{-8} Re^{4.429} \alpha^{0.920} \beta^{3.767} \delta^{0.2360}]^{0.1} \quad (4)$$

Dong et al. [9] take into account also the effect of the fin length, included in the parameter γ , with correlations of experimental data within a 10% of error:

$$f = 2.092 Re^{-0.281} \alpha^{-0.739} \beta^{0.972} \delta^{-0.78} \gamma^{-0.497} \quad (5)$$

However, the application of these last correlations is limited to a Reynolds number range from 500 to 7500, for short length aluminium heat exchangers manufactured with standard manufacturing techniques. When the aluminium pressure drop is compared to Manglik and Dong correlations in Fig. 10, there is a good match between Manglik and the results in the laminar region, but the current results show a transition region where the friction factor increases with the Re, departing from Manglik.

Figure 10 Fanning factor evolution for Aluminium, and comparison with correlations

The main reason for this disagreement lies into the increased roughness induced by the additive manufacturing. Indeed, as the roughness is not taken into account in CFD, the numerical results agree well with the Dong correlation.

When plotted in logarithmic scale as in Fig. 11, the experimental results show a behaviour following

Darcy in the laminar regime, and a transition to turbulence in Re lower than 2100. It is also interesting to see that the transition is triggered at earlier Reynolds for aluminium, which has an increased measured roughness compared to the Inconel sample.

Figure 11 Fanning factor evolution

This behaviour has already been observed by Stimpson [12] where additive manufactured mini channel pressure drop was measured. It has also been observed by Huang on pipes with a high relative roughness [13]. The fully turbulent region, which would have allowed the determination of the sand grain size, has not been measured in our experiments as the flowmeter range was limited. This range should be increased in future experiments.

5. THERMAL ANALYSIS

The thermal analysis concerns the study of the temperature variation of the fluid flowing in the CHX module while heated. The final objective is the determination of the forced convection heat transfer coefficient of the air, performing a heat balance. The temperature variation of the air flow can occur only in case there is a heat source. In this set-up, an electric heating plate is glued on the top wall of the CHX sample to provide energy by Joule effect, ensuring a uniform heating of the flow blowing inside the channel. All the temperature measurements were executed in stationary conditions, providing a Joule heating power equal to 130 W.

6. INFRARED THERMAL MEASUREMENTS

The infrared (IR) thermography has been exploited to retrieve the temperature distribution on the bottom surface of the CHX channel. The width of the investigation area is smaller (20 mm) than the real dimension of the sample (50 mm) as it includes only the free space available between the two rows of probes mounted in the channel. The acquisition was performed once the temperature distribution

along the sample reached stationary conditions. Fig. 12 and 13 show the temperature contours obtained for $\dot{m}=5$ g/s and $\dot{m}=10$ g/s. The main temperature gradient is present in the longitudinal direction; the transversal one can be considered negligible thanks to the presence of the insulation on the lateral sides of the sample.

Figure 12 Temperature contour for $\dot{m}=5$ g/s

The temperature distribution is increasing linearly along the aluminium channel, with a temperature gradient which is higher than the one obtained with the Inconel for the same operating conditions. This difference becomes even more relevant as the mass flow rate increases. For the same operating conditions, the aluminium always shows higher temperature levels: the temperature increases linearly to stabilize around a constant value at the end of the channel. For the Inconel, the trend of the profile is also linear, but both the absolute value of the temperature and the gradient along the surface are lower. It is interesting to comment the small decrease of temperature at the beginning of the channel, followed by an inversion of the trend. This effect is due to the cooling of the inlet fresh air combined with the heat produced by the heating plate: this generates an inflection point in the temperature trend which is evident only for the Inconel because of its higher resistance to the heat transfer.

Figure 13 Temperature contour for $\dot{m}=10$ g/s

7. INLET AND OUTLET TEMPERATURE

The temperature at the inlet section of the CHX module is measured through four thermocouples, each one placed on one of the different sides of the rectangular cross section of the channel (Fig. 4). The measurements show that the inlet temperature is uniform within an uncertainty interval equal to ± 0.6 °C. This happens for both the aluminium and the Inconel channels, as this temperature is independent from the material taken into account. The outlet temperature is monitored using nine thermocouples, displaced on a cross-shaped rake at the outlet section of the CHX module (Fig. 4). In this case, the results are dependent on the heat transfer mechanisms. Therefore, the outcome of the measurements is different for both the materials. The analysis has been led for both the vertical and the horizontal temperature profiles and the results discussed for each material. The temperature detected with the probes, located vertically, is expected to mirror the temperature distribution along the fins. Fig. 14 and 15 show the horizontal temperature profiles, in °C, scaled by the inlet temperature, obtained for the two different materials and the three reference mass flow rates.

Figure 14 Aluminium: horizontal outlet temperature profile

The Aluminium shows a uniform horizontal temperature distribution (Fig. 14): the maximum variation in temperature is around 0.5 °C and a small increase is always detected in the middle of the section. It can be observed also that the CFD results are underestimating the outlet temperature.

Figure 15 Inconel: horizontal outlet temperature profile

The Inconel exhibits quite different results (Fig. 15): there is an effective temperature gradient in the horizontal direction for all the mass flow rates and it is more significant as the flow velocity decreases. The highest gradient corresponds to the middle of the section because this is the region which is less influenced by border “effects”, such as losses through the ambient and dissipation due to the conductivity through the fins and the CHX case, depending on the properties of the material. This gradient is also reproduced numerically, although the CFD in the case of Inconel overestimates the experiments.

Regarding the vertical temperature profiles, it appears increasing from the bottom to the top of the section and the gradient is much more significant for the Inconel CHX channel (Fig. 16, 17).

Figure 16 Aluminium: vertical outlet temperature profile

This is mirroring the negative temperature gradient along the fins from the upper side, closer to the heating plate, to the bottom side. This is the result of both the cooling effect of the air flow blowing inside the channel and the conductive resistance of

the fins, depending on the material properties. However, the gradient is less evident for lower mass flow rates and for the Aluminium as, thanks to its high thermal conductivity, the fins are characterized by higher thermal efficiency, hence a lower temperature variation along their height. The maximum temperature difference measured for the Aluminium is 2.7 °C (Fig. 16), while for the Inconel is around 32.2 °C (Fig. 17). The comparison between experimental and numerical outlet vertical temperature profiles also show an overestimation of the temperature for Inconel, and an underestimation for Aluminium.

Figure 17 Inconel: vertical outlet temperature profile

8. HEAT TRANSFER COEFFICIENT

The principal objective of the thermal experimental campaign is to determine the convective heat transfer coefficient of the air flow inside the CHX channel.

The convective heat transfer coefficient, h_c , was calculated using a definition similar to Stimpson [12], and detailed in Eq. (6) to (9). As the experiments performed in this study have strong similarities with Stimpson, this definition is very well suited.

$$h_c = \frac{Q_{air}}{A_s \Delta T_{LM}} \quad (6)$$

$$Q_{air} = \dot{m} C_p (T_{out} - T_{in}) \quad (7)$$

$$\Delta T_{LM} = \frac{T_{out} - T_{in}}{\log\left(\frac{T_s - T_{in}}{T_s - T_{out}}\right)} \quad (8)$$

where A_s is the wetted surface area of the sample, ΔT_{LM} and Q_{air} is the heat transferred into the air as it passed through the sample. The temperature of the top surface of the sample T_s is measured from the exterior wall, and computed using a 1D conduction analysis to the sample external wall as described in Eq. (9)

$$T_s = T_{wall} - \frac{t_{wall}}{k_m} \left(\frac{Q_{Joule}}{A_{res}} \right) \quad (9)$$

Where T_{wall} is the mean temperature read by the thermocouples placed under the heating plate, T_{in} and T_{out} are the mean temperatures respectively at the inlet and outlet of the CHX sample, t_{wall} is the thickness of the exterior walls of the CHX sample, and k_m is the thermal conductivity coefficient of the material of the CHX module. Such definition allows also to take into account changes in the internal geometry, as the objective of NATHENA is to compare different fin designs. Finally, the use of Q_{air} instead of Q_J from the resistance takes into account the losses by natural convection through the bottom wall. However, this definition assumes a symmetric CHX element while the actual experiments are not (one side heated, one with losses by natural convection).

Results of the heat transfer coefficient are presented later in terms of a Nusselt number, Nu , computed using the air thermal conductivity and the hydraulic diameter. For the CFD, two definitions of the mean T_s and T_{out} are used; one using the temperatures averaged over the whole mesh (Mean in legend of Fig. 18), or using the temperatures averaged only from points at the same locations as the thermocouples (Exp. In legend of Fig. 18). As observed in Fig. 18, the heat transfer is enhanced for aluminum compared to Inconel, with approximately 5 times higher heat transfer coefficient. Hence, for the same amount of supplied Joule heating power, the best thermal efficiency, in terms of convective heat transfer coefficient, is expected to be obtained for the Aluminium CHX module. In terms of comparison with CFD, the simulations are underestimating the Nusselt for Aluminium while the Nusselt for Inconel is matching the experiments. Both definitions of the Nusselt show similar results, showing a small effect of the experimental discretization on the results. The underestimation of Aluminium might be related to roughness effects, more predominant in Aluminium samples.

Figure 18 Average Nusselt Number evolution

Regarding the thermal characterization, experimental results are usually presented in terms of Colburn factor j as function of the Reynolds number. It is an analogue of the Fanning factor for the heat transfer and it depends on other non-dimensional groups, such as: Stanton (St), Prandtl (Pr) and Nusselt (Nu) number. The complexity of the flow field generated in the CHX module makes difficult the predictability of these parameters, however, different attempts are available in literature. The non-dimensional analysis has been carried on only for the aerothermal characterization of the aluminium sample, due to the limitation of validity of the correlations to this material. This aspect is of critical importance, especially for the thermal investigation, strongly dependent on the thermal conductivity of the material. The Colburn factor correlation of Manglik and Berges [8]:

$$j = 0.6522Re^{-0.5403}\alpha^{-0.1541}\beta^{0.1499}\delta^{-0.0678} \times [1 + 5.269 \cdot 10^{-5}\alpha^{0.504}\beta^{0.0456}\delta^{-1.055}]^{0.1} \quad (11)$$

And Dong et al. [9] are compared similarly as for the Fanning factor:

$$j = 0.101Re^{-0.189}\alpha^{-0.488}\beta^{0.479}\delta^{-0.297}\gamma^{-0.315} \quad (13)$$

Applying the formulas of the definition for the Colburn factor on the experimental data obtained with the measurements as well as the numerical simulations, the outcome has been compared with the two correlations mentioned in Fig. 19. The general trend of the experimental Colburn fits better with Manglik, but the experimental decay is stronger, even stronger for the Colburn determined numerically. As both Colburn are lower than the correlation, one possible explanation for this underestimation is the definition of the heat transfer coefficient while having losses by natural convection on the bottom wall, which differs from the experimental conditions used for the derivation of the correlations [15].

Figure 19. Comparison of the experimental and numerical Colburn factor with correlations

9. MEASUREMENTS UNCERTAINTY

The uncertainty on the measured quantities is evaluated considering all the possible sources related to it: standard uncertainty, statistically depending on the number of samples analysed; and uncertainty depending on other information, such as calibration certificates, calculations, published information, common sense. These different contributions can be combined by root sum of the square and the result is known as combined standard uncertainty. Tab. 1 lists the values of uncertainty of the main measured quantities, in a confidence interval of 95%.

Table 1. Uncertainty of measured properties

Property	Uncertainty
\dot{m}	± 0.15 g/s
Δp	± 219.84 kPa
$T_{thermocouple}$	± 0.6 °C
$T_{IRcamera}$	± 1.4 °C
u	± 0.3 m/s

For properties calculated as a function of different measured quantities, the uncertainty is obtained on the basis of the law of error propagation: an output quantity error is determined on the basis of known errors of input quantities using an expansion of the model function in a Taylor series up to the first-order terms.

10. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORKS

The experimental campaign conducted at the VKI, in the framework of the European project NATHENA, concerns the aerothermal characterization of two off-set strip fins CHX modules, one in aluminium alloy and one in Inconel alloy. The principal aim is the determination of both the total pressure drop along the channel and the heat transfer coefficient for different mass flow rates. The results are compared to investigate on the influence of the material. In parallel, CFD simulations, reproducing the experimental scenarios, were performed, simulating only smooth walls.

The pressure losses, directly dependent on the mass flow rate, is more significant for the aluminium CHX module, as a consequence of its rougher surface. Due to the absence of simulation of the roughness, the CFD results are reproducing well the experiments at low flow rates, when the flow is only starting to become turbulent whereas at higher flow rates, when the flow reaches a fully turbulent regime, the CFD are underestimating the pressure losses. Future studies will be dedicated to introduce roughness effects in the simulations as well as more sophisticated experimental investigation of the roughness. Finally, the pressure losses of the aluminium module were deviating from correlations like Manglik, developed for standard manufactured CHX as the roughness introduced by the additive

manufacturing process is higher.

For a complete aeraulic investigation, the hot wire anemometry is exploited to determine the velocity profile at both the inlet and outlet sections of the CHX module.

The heat transfer coefficient is obtained following the definition introduced by Stimpson [12]. The temperature measurements are performed using both thermocouples and IR thermography. The results for the heat transfer coefficient show its direct dependence on the air mass flow. The heat transfer coefficient is higher for the aluminium channel than for the Inconel. This behaviour is dependent on the higher thermal resistivity of the latter material, which obstructs the heat transfer. This effect is also visible from the image of the contours obtained from the IR camera measurements. Both the absolute value of temperature and its gradients along the bottom surface of the sample are always lower for the Inconel compared to the aluminium, as proof of its poor conductivity.

The comparison with the CFD results showed an underestimation of the outlet temperatures and the heat transfer coefficient compared to the experiments for Aluminium. For Inconel, there is an overestimation of the outlet temperatures while the Nusselt determined from CFD matches well the experimental values. Future works will investigate the effect of the turbulence models in the simulations and include roughness to see how these can affect the comparison with experiments.

The next step of the project is a new experimental campaign to test other CHX modules characterized by different internal geometries, materials, surface finish and frontal cross section area for the creation of a data base for a parametric study of the thermal and aeraulic efficiency of additive manufacturing CHX modules.

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NOMENCLATURE

A_{res}	resistance surface	[m ²]
A_s	total wetted area	[m ²]
b	channel width	[mm]
D_h	hydraulic diameter	[mm]
d	flow length	[mm]
h	channel height	[mm]
h_c	heat transfer coefficient	[W/m ² K]
k	thermal conductivity	[W/mK]
L	channel longitudinal length	[mm]
l	fins length	[mm]
N_{fin}	Number of fins	[-]
\dot{m}	mass flow rate	[g/s]
p	static pressure	[Pa]
\dot{Q}	heat power	[W]
\dot{q}	heat flux	[W/m ²]
Ra	profile surface roughness	[μm]
s	fins spacing	[mm]
T_{in}	Inlet mean temperature	[°C]
T_{out}	Outlet mean temperature	[°C]
T_s	surface mean temperature	[°C]
T_{wall}	top wall mean temperature	[°C]
t	fins thickness	[mm]
t_{wall}	wall thickness	[mm]
u	flow velocity	[m/s]
V	volume	[m ³]

Greek letters

α	non-dimensional parameter, s/h
β	non-dimensional parameter, t/l
δ	non-dimensional parameter, t/s

γ non-dimensional parameter, d/l

η compactness, A/V

ρ flow density [kg/m³]

Non-dimensional numbers

f Fanning factor

j Colburn factor

Nu Nusselt number

Pr Prandtl number

Re Reynolds number

St Stanton number

Acronyms

AM Additive Manufacturing

CHX Compact Heat Exchanger

TI Turbulence Intensity